

Influence of flag leaf area on rice seed germinability and vigor

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We studied the relationship between flag leaf area and panicle size, panicle weight, 1,000-grain weight, germination, and vigor in short-duration ADT36, TKM9, and IR50 rices. Flag leaf areas were 10.50-26.72 cm² in ADT36, 11.61-33.75 cm² in TKM9, and 6.50-19.95 cm² in IR50.

The results indicate a close relationship between flag leaf area and yield and quality parameters (see table).

In ADT36, correlations between flag leaf area for all parameters were

Correlations between flag leaf area and yield and quality parameters of 3 short-duration rices. Tamil Nadu, India, 1989.

Variety	Leaf area (cm)	Panicle size	Panicle weight	1,000-grain weight	Germination	Vigor index
ADT36		0.9184**	0.9150**	0.8220**	0.7120**	0.6365**
TKM9	11.61-28.75	0.9634**	0.8916**	-0.4236*	0.4559*	0.5122*
	>28.75	-0.8434**	-0.3889	-	-0.6807**	-0.8036**
IR50	6.50-14.30	0.8718**	0.9066**	0.9631**	0.6142**	0.9485**
	>14.30	-0.9224**	0.8550**	-0.7910**		

positive and highly significant. In TKM9, the correlations for all parameters except 1,000-grain weight were positive and significant for flag leaf areas 11.61-28.75 cm²; large flag leaf areas showed significantly negative correlations. In the case of 1,000-grain weight in TKM9 there was a significant correlation with leaf areas 11.61-28.75 cm²; thereafter the correlation was not significant.

In IR50, the correlations between flag leaf area and panicle weight, germination, and vigor index were positive and significant. For flag leaf areas 6.50-14.30 cm², the correlations with panicle size and 1,000-grain weight were positive and significant; leaf areas 15.65-19.95 cm² had negative correlations. □

Heterosis and heterobeltiosis for five morphoanatomical characters of rice panicle

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We studied five morphoanatomical characters of the rice panicle in 34 parents and their 43 progeny hybrids. The characters were inner vascular bundle (IVB) and outer vascular bundle (OVB) just below the neck node, culm diameter (CD), medullary cavity diameter (MC), and culm thickness (CT). The number of vascular bundles is correlated positively with the number of primary branches (where heavier grains are located). Higher numbers of vascular bundles possibly indicate a better transport system.

Parents consisted of 9 IR varieties and lines, 10 other indicas, 5 *glaberrima* accessions, and 10 upland lines derived from an anther-cultured Moroberekan/Palawan cross.

Parents and their hybrids were grown in the field and greenhouse during 1988 dry season. Data from 10 primary tillers of each parent and

hybrid were recorded when panicles emerged completely from the flag leaf sheath.

Numbers of IVB and OVB were almost the same in IR and indica varieties; numbers of OVB were higher in *glaberrima* and upland lines. OVB/IVB ratios varied from 1.3 to 1.7 in *glaberrima* and upland rices; ratios were almost 1.0 in IR varieties.

Estimates of overall degree and direction of heterosis (F₁-P) were significant and positive for IVB (1.36**) and OVB (0.67*), indicating dominance of higher values. Estimates for CD (0.05), MC (0.09), and CT (-0.02) were not significant.

Values for individual F₁ families differed from overall estimates for heterosis in IVB and OVB (see figure).

Heterosis (H) and heterobeltiosis (Hb) for inner vascular bundle (IVB) and outer vascular bundle (OVB) in 43 crosses. IRRI, 1988 dry season.

The F_1 means deviated conspicuously from parental and mid-parental values, indicating nonadditive gene action for these two characters. Substantial heterosis in the desirable direction was observed in IVB and OVB, which are related to higher numbers of primary branches.

The table shows the mean value for four selected crosses and their parents. All the crosses had 25 or more IVB, compared to 17.7 for the parental mean. They also exhibited positive heterosis and heterobeltiosis. Most of the crosses had positive heterosis and negative heterobeltiosis for OVB, CD, and MC, but both estimates were negative for CT. Rewa 353-2/IR30 showed positive heterosis and heterobeltiosis for all characters except CT.

The potence ratio indicated overdominance for IVB, OVB, CD, and MD and partial dominance for CT. □

Mean values of 5 panicle characters in selected hybrids and their parents, percentage of heterosis and heterobeltiosis, and estimates of potence ratio. IRR, 1989.

Parent or cross	Inner vascular bundle (no.)		Outer vascular bundle (no.)		Culm diameter (mm)		Medullary cavity (mm)		Culm thickness (mm)	
	H	Hb	H	Hb	H	Hb	H	Hb	H	Hb
IR30	(1)	18.3	18.9		2.08		1.51			0.28
IR29692-117-1-2-2	(2)	16.4	20.2		2.00		1.29			0.35
IR28211-43-1-1-2	(3)	20.5	24.9		2.32		1.68			0.32
IR29429-13-3-13-1-3	(4)	20.4	21.8		2.72		2.06			0.33
IR47705-AC5-1	(5)	21.0	31.8		2.65		1.81			0.42
IR47705-AC5	(6)	22.8	30.4		2.71		1.91			0.40
Rewa 353-2	(7)	20.1	20.0		2.37		1.76			0.30
IR36 (check)		15.1	17.6		1.72		1.21			0.26
Mean		19.3	23.2		2.32		1.65			0.34
Mean (over 34 parents)		17.7	22.5		2.21		1.50			0.35
LSD (0.05)		1.5	2.2		0.15		0.14			0.03
Cross:										
6 × 2		25.4	28.3		2.54		1.83			0.36
5 × 4		25.0	28.2		2.69		2.00			0.34
5 × 3		25.7	30.5		2.52		1.80			0.36
7 × 1		25.2	23.1		2.46		1.86			0.30
Mean		25.3	27.5		2.55		1.87			0.34
Mean (over 43 crosses)		19.0	23.2		2.26		1.60			0.33
LSD (0.05)		1.5	1.5		0.10		0.09			0.02
Heterosis (H) and Heterobeltiosis (Hb)	H	Hb	H	Hb	H	Hb	H	Hb	H	Hb
6 × 2	29.6	11.4	11.9	-6.9	8.2	-6.1	14.4	-4.1	-7.9	-15.2
5 × 4	20.7	19.1	5.3	-11.3	0.2	-1.1	3.2	-3.1	-10.6	-20.3
5 × 3	23.9	22.4	7.6	-4.1	1.3	-4.9	3.5	-0.3	-4.2	-15.0
7 × 1	31.1	22.2	18.8	15.5	10.6	3.9	13.8	5.6	1.4	-1.7
LSD (0.05)	2.1	2.2	2.6	5.1	2.2	1.9	2.7	1.9	2.2	3.5
Potence ratio										
6 × 2		-19.3	-25.2		-2.3		-1.5			-0.5
5 × 4		-20.5	-26.7		-2.7		-1.9			-0.5
5 × 3		-20.5	-28.3		-2.5		-1.7			-0.4
7 × 1		-18.9	-19.3		-2.1		-1.5			-0.3

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Grain quality and nutritional value

Inheritance of grain length, width, thickness, and weight in Pakistan Basmati/IR1469 and Pakistan Basmati/Paizam 242

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Parents, F_1 s, and F_2 s (500 plants each) were raised during 1988 wet season at CRRRI, Cuttack. Mature panicles were collected from individual plants. Three seeds from each plant were measured for grain length, width, and thickness. Hundred-grain weight was recorded.

In Pakistan Basmati/IR1469, F_1 grain length, width, and thickness were around the mid-parent value; F_2

maximum frequencies were around the mean (Table 1). Grain width showed overdominance in the F_1 and F_2 . In P. Basmati/Paizam 242, maximum frequency for grain length was around

Table 1. Means for grain length, width, thickness, grain weight of P. Basmati/IR1469 and P. Basmati, Paizam 242. CRRRI, India, 1988 wet season.

Cross characters	Parents		F_1 s	F_2 s					
	P_1	P_2		Mean	Range	Variance	SE	CV (%)	
<i>P. Basmati/IR1469</i>	<i>P. Basmati</i>	<i>IR1469</i>							
Grain length (mm)	11.42	8.67	10.00	9.88	8.10 - 12.38	5601.3	3.34	7.5	
Grain width (mm)	2.26	3.00	2.79	2.69	2.02 - 3.05	351.7	0.84	6.9	
Grain thickness (mm)	1.91	2.11	2.06	2.02	1.73 - 2.23	65.5	0.36	4.0	
100-grain weight (g)	2.38	2.68	2.77	2.64	1.40 - 3.80	14.9	0.17	1.4	
<i>P. Basmati/Paizam 242</i>	<i>P. Basmati</i>	<i>Paizam 242</i>							
Grain length (mm)	11.42	7.51	9.04	9.04	7.61 - 11.41	4311.0	2.91	7.2	
Grain width (mm)	2.26	2.57	2.52	2.43	2.05 - 2.80	227.4	0.67	6.2	
Grain thickness (mm)	1.91	1.85	1.92	1.88	1.58 - 2.06	55.8	0.33	3.9	
100-grain weight (g)	2.38	1.64	2.12	2.03	1.25 - 2.85	910.4	3.96	14.8	